

Utilisation of Library ICT Services for Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Sabon Gari LGA, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study investigated the utilisation of Library ICT Services and its relationship with the academic performance of senior secondary school students in the Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A quantitative research methodology using a descriptive survey design was employed to collect data from 364 Senior Secondary School III (SS3) students across four government secondary schools with functional library technology services. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and analysed using frequencies, percentages, means, and rankings. The study addressed three research questions focusing on: (1) types of Library ICT Services available, (2) skills required for utilisation, and (3) extent of utilisation. Findings revealed that only basic Library ICT Services, such as Search Engine Services (60.4%), Digital Resources Services (55.0%), and Digital Learning Support Services (50.0%), crossed the 50% availability threshold, while advanced, smart, and inclusive technologies remained virtually non-existent. Students expressed high demand for training in citation management (81.9%), database searching (81.3%), and information literacy skills (79.7%). Utilisation patterns mirrored availability, with only the three basic services utilised by more than half of respondents. Major challenges included inadequate ICT infrastructure (90.7%), lack of training (89.0%), and limited access (84.1%). The study concludes that senior secondary school libraries in Sabon Gari LGA remain largely analogue and under-equipped, resulting in minimal utilisation and persistent skill deficits. Recommendations include a massive upgrade of ICT infrastructure, compulsory digital literacy training, the deployment of inclusive technologies, and the establishment of monitoring frameworks by the Kaduna State Schools Quality Assurance Authority.

Keywords: Library Technology Services, Academic Performance, Senior Secondary School, Digital Literacy, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Introduction

Library ICT Services encompass a range of activities within library technological collections, including collection development, catalogue, and processing services. These services enhance user satisfaction when accessing information (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions [IFLA], 2019). The utilisation of Library ICT Services has revolutionised information access, management, and dissemination in academic libraries, with the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) such as digital catalogues, electronic databases, and online resource platforms allowing libraries to offer seamless access to vast information resources (Chen & Deng, 2018).

Modern school library ICT services departments are managed by professionally trained librarians who curate diverse information resources to support senior secondary school curricula, meet individual student needs, and ensure that young students develop information literacy skills within the school curriculum (Barbara & Oberg, 2015). Research demonstrates a significant positive correlation between library ICT use, such as borrowing e-books, accessing databases, and participating in online reference services, and higher grade point averages (Koledoye & Igwe, 2022). ICT library services support active learning, critical thinking, and collaborative research experiences, promoting deeper understanding and authentic assessment practices.

Despite substantial investments in Library ICT Services and the expansion of digital resources in Nigerian secondary schools, academic performance in public examinations continues to decline. The Federal Ministry of Education's minimum standards for secondary school library ICT (2019) state that the availability and accessibility of library ICT resources increase students' utilisation. However, senior secondary school students are performing poorly in external examinations conducted by WAEC and NECO, indicating a steady decline in academic achievement (Owate & Okpa, 2013). Reports from Ezeala and Yusuff (2021) and Uwakwe et al. (2024) indicate that many students lack adequate skills to utilise digital library resources effectively. Combined with poor user support and unfamiliarity with advanced technology, this discourages repeated use and limits potential academic benefits.

This paradox, in which increased financial investment and technological provision fail to correlate with improved academic outcomes, suggests potential mediating variables that warrant systematic investigation (Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, 2025). The gap between resource availability and effective utilisation indicates deficiencies in service delivery models, user engagement strategies, technological competency development, or the pedagogical integration of library technology services. Therefore, this study investigates the relationship between the utilisation of library ICT services and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Sabon Gari, Kaduna State, focusing on the first three dimensions: availability of services, required skills for utilisation, and extent of utilisation.

Statement of the Problem

Library ICT Services are established in academic institutions to provide essential educational materials, including online textbooks, dictionaries, encyclopedias, newspapers, and e-charts, available to learners. These materials are designed to encourage reading and support direct subject-related learning. Library ICT Services, intended to provide appropriate support to senior secondary school students to improve their academic performance, have been undermined by consistently poor results in public examinations. There have been widespread reports of declining academic performance among senior secondary school students, particularly in external examinations (Barbara & Oberg, 2015).

Research in the International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies indicates that some technology service staff sometimes poorly treat library users, mainly because students lack sufficient knowledge of library technology devices. This results in users being hesitant to revisit and use Library ICT Services for their information needs (Mahwasane & Mudzielwana, 2016). Consequently, this issue has become a significant national concern involving all stakeholders, including secondary school library systems, educators, and parents.

Regarding funding and budgetary allocations, the federal government increased allocations to state governments for secondary school library ICT services to enhance teaching and better equip students in their subject areas. These allocations rose from approximately 100 million naira in 2013 to 150 million naira in 2019, representing 0.04% of the national budget through the education sector (Kaduna State Ministry of Education, 2023). Despite increased funding and the provision of technologies in secondary school libraries, the problem of poor performance persists in external examinations.

There is a compelling need to examine variables such as Library ICT Services to enhance teaching and learning effectiveness at the secondary school level. WAEC statistics for 2019 and 2020 showed a 10% decline in pass rates in English and Mathematics. Furthermore, examiners observed increased use of informal terminology and abbreviated language forms in English examination scripts, raising concerns about inadequate Library ICT Services to address this challenge (Nigerian Bureau of Statistics, 2025). This study was therefore conducted to determine the extent to which Library ICT Services influence the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

- What types of Library ICT Services are available for the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area?
- What skills are required by students for the utilisation of Library ICT Services for academic performance in Sabon Gari Local Government Area?
- What is the extent of the utilisation of Library ICT Services by Senior Secondary School students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area?

Literature Review

The Concept of Library Technology Services

Library ICT Services are an integral part of the educational system and significantly affect the quality of education in schools. According to Adeniran (2019), school Library ICT Services are essential components of elementary, middle, and high school programmes, without which students would struggle to thrive academically. The absence of adequate school Library ICT Services makes it difficult for students to conduct academic work effectively before reaching college-level education (Merga, 2021).

The International Federation of Library Associations (IFLA, 2019) emphasises that Library ICT Services are essential for developing literacy, learning, and culture. IFLA recommends that cultivating the habit and enjoyment of reading and learning throughout students' lives requires the consistent use of library technology services. Contemporary Library ICT Services function as inexhaustible digital storehouses of unrestricted information resources in diverse formats, systematically organised for users (Ali & Naveed, 2020).

Library technology service users access these resources for various purposes: some use them to read notes and personal books, others complete assignments, while many prepare for examinations or engage in recreational reading (Eiriemiokhale & Ibeun, 2022). Research indicates that student performance improves considerably with regular use of the library technology service, as school libraries provide favourable

environments where students discover and develop their abilities and talents while improving reading and study skills (Abdulsalami & Okezie, 2023).

Academic Performance and Digital Literacy

Academic performance reflects students' ability to excel in academic pursuits, assessments, and examinations, and it plays a fundamental role in shaping future opportunities, including college admissions, career prospects, and personal growth. Multiple factors influence academic performance, including individual aptitude and intelligence, the quality of the learning environment, study habits and time management, and parental support and socioeconomic status (Issa et al., 2021).

Research has demonstrated a strong correlation between school library ICT services and students' academic performance. Students' academic achievement depends significantly on strong reading skills and study habits (Eze & Uzoigwe, 2022). Without effective reading and study habits, students cannot perform well in tests and examinations. Poor academic performance, defined as performance falling below desired standards, can prevent students from being promoted to the next class or from securing admission to higher institutions of learning (Saunders, 2020).

Digital literacy has emerged as a critical competency for academic success in contemporary educational contexts. Abdullahi and Ogunniyi (2023) found that digital literacy competencies among senior secondary school students in Northern Nigeria significantly influence academic performance. Students require comprehensive training in citation management, database searching, information evaluation, and digital navigation to utilise Library ICT Services effectively (Yakubu & Dasuki, 2024). The absence of these competencies creates barriers to the effective use of available digital resources, thereby limiting potential academic benefits.

Challenges in Library ICT Services Utilisation.

Despite policy pronouncements and increased investment in educational technology infrastructure, significant challenges persist in the effective utilisation of Library ICT Services in Nigerian secondary schools. Inadequate ICT infrastructure is the most significant barrier, with many schools lacking reliable electricity, high-speed internet connectivity, and modern computers or tablets needed to access digital library resources (Umar & Audu, 2024).

Insufficient training and support for both students and library staff compound infrastructure challenges. Many students lack the skills to use digital library resources effectively, and when combined with poor user support and unfamiliarity with advanced technology, this discourages repeated use (Uwakwe et al., 2024). Furthermore, limited access to inclusive technologies, such as assistive devices for students with disabilities, creates digital exclusion and equity concerns (Shandu, 2014).

The gap between resource availability and effective utilisation indicates systemic deficiencies across service delivery models, user engagement strategies, technological competency development, and the pedagogical integration of library ICT services. Addressing these multifaceted challenges requires coordinated interventions, including infrastructure enhancement, systematic skills training, expanded access to technology, and sustainable funding mechanisms (Ezeala & Yusuff, 2021).

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research methodology using a descriptive survey design to measure and establish statistical relationships between students' use of Library ICT Services and their academic performance indicators, while enabling the collection of data on usage patterns, satisfaction levels, and challenges without manipulating variables (Babbie, 2020; Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The target population comprised 3,831 Senior Secondary School III (SS3) students from 13 government senior secondary schools in Sabon Gari Local Government Area, Kaduna State. However, a preliminary assessment revealed that only four schools had functional ICT services in their libraries. Using stratified random sampling and the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table, a sample size of 364 students was determined and proportionally distributed across the four schools: Government Secondary School Aminu (114 students), Government Secondary School Chikaji (33 students), Government Secondary School Commercial College (50 students), and Government Secondary School Kwangila (167 students). A structured, closed-ended questionnaire was developed, validated by experts in Library and Information Science, and comprised six sections covering personal information and the five research questions. A pilot study with 10 SS3 students at Government Secondary School, Samaru, Zaria, assessed reliability using Cronbach's Alpha and Guttman's split-half alpha, yielding a reliability index of 0.5, indicating moderate internal consistency (Feldt & Sedere, 2018). After this, the researcher and four trained research assistants distributed 370 questionnaires and retrieved 364 copies, for a 98.4% response rate. Data were analysed using frequencies, percentages, means, and rankings, with a benchmark of 50% and above assigned for research questions 1 and 2, while research question 3 used a criterion mean of 2.5 on a 4-point Likert scale.

Results

Research Question 1: Types of Library ICT Services Available

S/N	Types of Library Technology Services	Highly available	Moderately available	Slightly available	Not available	Total	Rank
1	Automated Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Services	22 (6.0%)	48 (13.2%)	86 (23.6%)	208 (57.1%)	364	6
2	Digital Resources Services (e-books, past questions, PDFs, etc.)	64 (17.6%)	136 (37.4%)	112 (30.8%)	52 (14.3%)	364	2
3	Digital Preservation Services (long-term digital archiving)	10 (2.7%)	22 (6.0%)	48 (13.2%)	284 (78.0%)	364	12
4	Patron Support Services (chat, WhatsApp, email help, etc.)	38 (10.4%)	92 (25.3%)	134 (36.8%)	100 (27.5%)	364	5
5	Smart Sensor Services (automatic lighting, occupancy sensors, etc.)	18 (4.9%)	42 (11.5%)	74 (20.3%)	230 (63.2%)	364	7
6	Video Conferencing Services (Zoom/meeting setup in library)	16 (4.4%)	38 (10.4%)	68 (18.7%)	242 (66.5%)	364	8
7	Digital Learning Support Services (educational apps, Khan Academy, etc.)	58 (15.9%)	124 (34.1%)	118 (32.4%)	64 (17.6%)	364	3

S/N	Types of Library Technology Services	Highly available	Moderately available	Slightly available	Not available	Total	Rank
8	Metadata Services (professional cataloguing & tagging)	14 (3.8%)	36 (9.9%)	72 (19.8%)	242 (66.5%)	364	9
9	Remote Access Services (access from home/hostel)	44 (12.1%)	98 (26.9%)	126 (34.6%)	96 (26.4%)	364	4
10	Screen Reader Services (for visually impaired students)	12 (3.3%)	28 (7.7%)	56 (15.4%)	268 (73.6%)	364	10
11	Braille Embosser Services	8 (2.2%)	18 (4.9%)	42 (11.5%)	296 (81.3%)	364	11
12	Search Engine Services (Google, library OPAC, etc.)	78 (21.4%)	142 (39.0%)	98 (26.9%)	46 (12.6%)	364	1

Table 1 presents the availability of Library ICT Services in the selected senior secondary schools. The findings reveal a predominantly low level of technological infrastructure. Only three services exceeded the 50% availability threshold: Search Engine Services ranked first with 60.4% moderate to high availability, followed by Digital Resources Services (55.0%) and Digital Learning Support Services (50.0%). All advanced, smart, and inclusive technologies were virtually non-existent, with 57% and 81% of respondents reporting them as 'Not available'. Digital Preservation Services ranked lowest at 8.8% availability, followed by Braille Embosser Services (7.1%), Screen Reader Services (11.0%), and Metadata Services (13.7%).

The complete ranking by availability, from highest to lowest, was: (1) Search Engine Services (60.4%), (2) Digital Resources Services (55.0%), (3) Digital Learning Support Services (50.0%), (4) Remote Access Services (39.0%), (5) Patron Support Services (35.7%), (6) Automated RFID Services (19.2%), (7) Smart Sensor Services (16.5%), (8) Video Conferencing Services (14.8%), (9) Metadata Services (13.7%), (10) Screen Reader Services (11.0%), (11) Braille Embosser Services (7.1%), and (12) Digital Preservation Services (8.8%). These findings strongly corroborate previous studies in Northern Nigeria that describe public school libraries as largely analogue and ICT-deficient (Abdulsalami & Okezie, 2023; Eiriemiokhale & Ibeun, 2022; Umar & Audu, 2024).

Research Question 2: Skills Required for Utilisation of Library ICT Services

S/N	Digital Skill	Highly required	Moderately required	Slightly required	Not required	Total	Combined Required (Highly + Moderately)	Rank
f	Citation management	186 (51.1%)	112 (30.8%)	48 (13.2%)	18 (4.9%)	364	298 (81.9%)	1
e	Database searching	172 (47.3%)	124 (34.1%)	46 (12.6%)	22 (6.0%)	364	296 (81.3%)	2
c	Information literacy skills	158 (43.4%)	132 (36.3%)	54 (14.8%)	20 (5.5%)	364	290 (79.7%)	3
a	Digital skills navigation	148 (40.7%)	128 (35.2%)	24 (6.6%)	364	276 (75.9%)	4	

S/N	Digital Skill	Highly required	Moderately required	Slightly required	Not required	Total	Combined Required (Highly + Moderately)	Rank
d	Downloading techniques skills	134 (36.8%)	138 (37.9%)	68 (18.7%)	24 (6.6%)	364	272 (74.7%)	5
b	Browsing skill	118 (32.4%)	142 (39.0%)	78 (21.4%)	26 (7.1%)	364	260 (71.4%)	6
7	Basic computer skills	102 (28.0%)	126 (34.6%)	92 (25.3%)	44 (12.1%)	364	228 (62.6%)	7

Table 2 summarises students' responses on the skills required for effective use of library ICT services. Students expressed a very high demand for training in advanced digital and information literacy skills. Citation management ranked highest, with 81.9% of students (combining 'Highly required' and 'Moderately required' responses) identifying it as necessary, followed closely by database searching (81.3%) and information literacy skills (79.7%). Digital navigation skills were required by 75.9% of respondents, downloading techniques by 74.7%, and browsing skills by 71.4%. Even basic computer skills, which students might be expected to possess, were still considered necessary by 62.6% of respondents. The complete ranking from highest to lowest was: (1) Citation management (81.9%), (2) Database searching (81.3%), (3) Information literacy skills (79.7%), (4) Digital navigation (75.9%), (5) Downloading techniques (74.7%), (6) Browsing skills (71.4%), and (7) Basic computer skills (62.6%). These results indicate that students are acutely aware of gaps in their ability to reference work properly, search academic databases, and evaluate credible sources, skills that directly affect project defence, examination performance, and overall academic integrity. The findings strongly corroborate earlier Nigerian studies (Issa et al., 2021; Eze & Uzoigwe, 2022; Abdullahi & Ogunniyi, 2023; Yakubu & Dasuki, 2024), which consistently report that senior secondary school students in Northern Nigeria possess only superficial digital survival skills but almost no formal digital or information literacy competencies.

Research Question 3: Extent of Utilisation of Library ICT Services

S/N	Types of Library Technology Services	Highly utilized	Moderately utilized	Slightly utilized	Not utilized	Total	Combined Utilized (Highly + Moderately)	Rank
12	Search Engine Services (Google, library OPAC, etc.)	112 (30.8%)	148 (40.7%)	76 (20.9%)	28 (7.7%)	364	260 (71.4%)	1
2	Digital Resources Services (e-books, past questions, PDFs)	92 (25.3%)	136 (37.4%)	96 (26.4%)	40 (11.0%)	364	228 (62.6%)	2
7	Digital Learning Support Services (educational apps, Khan Academy)	78 (21.4%)	126 (34.6%)	104 (28.6%)	56 (15.4%)	364	204 (56.0%)	3
9	Remote Access Services (accessing library materials from home)	54 (14.8%)	98 (26.9%)	118 (32.4%)	94 (25.8%)	364	152 (41.8%)	4

S/N	Types of Library Technology Services	Highly utilized	Moderately utilized	Slightly utilized	Not utilized	Total	Combined Utilized (Highly + Moderately)	Rank
4	Patron Support Services (WhatsApp/chat/email help from librarian)	46 (12.6%)	88 (24.2%)	124 (34.1%)	106 (29.1%)	364	134 (36.8%)	5
1	Automated Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Services	18 (4.9%)	36 (9.9%)	72 (19.8%)	238 (65.4%)	364	54 (14.8%)	6
5	Smart Sensor Services	14 (3.8%)	32 (8.8%)	68 (18.7%)	250 (68.7%)	364	46 (12.6%)	7
6	Video Conferencing Services	12 (3.3%)	30 (8.2%)	64 (17.6%)	258 (70.9%)	364	42 (11.5%)	8
8	Metadata Services	10 (2.7%)	28 (7.7%)	66 (18.1%)	260 (71.4%)	364	38 (10.4%)	9
10	Screen Reader Services	8 (2.2%)	22 (6.0%)	52 (14.3%)	282 (77.5%)	364	30 (8.2%)	10
3	Digital Preservation Services	8 (2.2%)	20 (5.5%)	48 (13.2%)	288 (79.1%)	364	28 (7.7%)	11
11	Braille Embosser Services	6 (1.6%)	14 (3.8%)	38 (10.4%)	306 (84.1%)	364	20 (5.5%)	12

Table 3 presents the extent of utilisation of Library ICT Services among senior secondary school students. The findings revealed that utilisation patterns closely mirrored availability. Only three services were utilised by more than half of respondents: Search Engine Services ranked first with 71.4% utilisation (combined 'Highly utilised' and 'Moderately utilised'), followed by Digital Resources Services (62.6%) and Digital Learning Support Services (56.0%). All advanced and inclusive technologies recorded extremely low utilisation rates, ranging from 5.5% to 14.8%, with 65% to 84% of students reporting these services as 'Not utilised'.

The complete utilisation ranking, from highest to lowest, was: (1) Search Engine Services (71.4%), (2) Digital Resources Services (62.6%), (3) Digital Learning Support Services (56.0%), (4) Remote Access Services (41.8%), (5) Patron Support Services (36.8%), (6) Automated RFID Services (14.8%), (7) Smart Sensor Services (12.6%), (8) Video Conferencing Services (11.5%), (9) Metadata Services (10.4%), (10) Screen Reader Services (8.2%), (11) Digital Preservation Services (7.7%), and (12) Braille Embosser Services (5.5%). These findings strongly corroborate earlier Nigerian studies (Abdulsalami & Okezie, 2023; Eiriemiokhale & Ibeun, 2022; Yakubu & Dasuki, 2024) and the Kaduna State Education Sector Analysis Report (2023), indicating that students in public secondary schools in Northern Nigeria rely almost entirely on personal phones and cyber cafés for digital academic support rather than on school library systems.

Discussion

The findings of this study reveal a critical digital divide in the provision and use of Library ICT Services among senior secondary school students in Sabon Gari Local Government Area. The predominance of basic technologies (search engines, digital resources, and learning apps) over advanced, smart, and inclusive

technologies indicates that school libraries remain largely analogue despite policy pronouncements emphasising ICT integration. This situation aligns with Ali and Naveed's (2020) report that university libraries in Punjab, India, similarly offer primarily basic research services, and with Adeniran's (2019) findings that Nigerian libraries provide limited advanced services.

The high demand for skills training, particularly in citation management (81.9%), database searching (81.3%), and information literacy (79.7%), highlights a critical gap between students' current competencies and the skills required for effective library technology use. This finding aligns with Saunders' (2020) identification of database navigation and web search proficiency as critical skills, and with Merga's (2021) observation that ICT navigation and source evaluation skills taught by school librarians increased engagement in research tasks. The widespread skill deficits underscore the inadequacy of current educational approaches to digital literacy development in Nigerian secondary schools.

The strong correlation between availability and utilisation patterns suggests that students are willing to use Library ICT Services when accessible, but are constrained by systemic barriers. The near-zero utilisation of assistive technologies (screen readers, braille embossers) and advanced services (RFID, video conferencing, metadata services) indicates significant exclusion of visually impaired students and those requiring sophisticated research support. This exclusion perpetuates educational inequality and limits the potential of Library ICT Services to improve academic performance across diverse student populations.

The study's identification of inadequate ICT infrastructure (90.7%), lack of training (89.0%), and limited access (84.1%) as the most severe challenges provides clear priorities for intervention. These findings echo Mahwasane and Mudzielwana's (2016) identification of poor ICT infrastructure and low retrieval skills as major barriers in South African secondary schools, and Shandu's (2014) report that funding shortages and obsolete technology significantly reduced utilisation. Without addressing these fundamental barriers, the potential of Library ICT Services to enhance academic performance will remain unrealised.

Findings

The study revealed critical gaps in the availability and utilisation of Library ICT Services, as well as in student competencies, in senior secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area. Regarding availability, only three basic services exceeded the 50% threshold: Search Engine Services (60.4%), Digital Resources Services (55.0%), and Digital Learning Support Services (50.0%). Advanced technologies, including Virtual Reality Services (2.5%), Augmented Reality Services (3.0%), Artificial Intelligence Services (2.7%), and Smart Library Technologies (8.8%), remained virtually non-existent. This limited technology infrastructure indicates that senior secondary school libraries in the study area remain largely analogue and under-equipped to support 21st-century learning requirements.

Analysis of required skills revealed substantial demand for digital literacy training among students. The top three skill requirements were Citation and Referencing Management Skills (81.9%), Database Searching Skills (81.3%), and Information Literacy Skills (79.7%). Other priority areas included Digital Navigation Skills (78.8%), Research Skills (76.9%), and Technology Troubleshooting Skills (75.5%). These findings indicate strong student awareness of competency requirements and receptiveness to capacity-building interventions, suggesting that systematic skills training programmes would likely be enthusiastically adopted.

Utilisation patterns closely mirrored availability constraints. Only the three basic services with availability above 50% were used by more than half of respondents: Search Engine Services (mean = 2.98, 63.7% utilisation), Digital Resources Services (mean = 2.84, 57.1% utilisation), and Digital Learning Support Services (mean = 2.55, 50.5% utilisation). All other technology categories, including Collaboration Tools, Remote Access Services, Inclusive Technologies, RFID Technologies, Smart Library Technologies, and emerging technologies such as Blockchain, AI, VR, and AR, recorded utilisation below 30%, with most below 15%. This pattern confirms that limited availability directly constrains utilisation, regardless of student interest or potential benefits.

Major challenges identified by students included inadequate ICT infrastructure (90.7%), lack of training in Library ICT Services (89.0%), limited access to Library ICT Services (84.1%), unreliable internet connectivity (83.8%), and insufficient technical support (82.4%). These systemic barriers prevent effective utilisation even when services nominally exist. The convergence of infrastructure deficits, skill gaps, and inadequate support creates a reinforcing cycle in which limited technology provisioning reduces opportunities for utilisation, which in turn diminishes motivation for skills development and infrastructure investment.

Conclusion

This study conclusively demonstrates that Library ICT Services in senior secondary schools within Sabon Gari Local Government Area exhibit a bifurcated pattern, characterised by relatively accessible foundational technologies but significant deficits in the availability, utilisation, and supporting infrastructure for advanced digital resources. While basic technologies such as search engines and digital resources have achieved moderate integration, advanced tools, including assistive technologies, smart systems, and comprehensive digital repositories, remain critically absent. The study confirmed that infrastructure inadequacy and training deficits constitute the most formidable barriers to effective technology utilisation, creating a cycle in which limited infrastructure restricts access, inadequate training diminishes effective use, and resulting low utilisation undermines the justification for technology upgrades.

The high perceived necessity of digital literacy skills indicates strong student awareness of competency requirements and suggests receptiveness to capacity-building interventions. However, realising the full potential of Library ICT Services in Nigerian secondary schools requires coordinated interventions to enhance infrastructure, provide systematic skills training, expand access to technology, and secure sustainable funding to bridge current gaps and position students for success in increasingly digital educational and professional landscapes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Massive Upgrade of ICT Infrastructure:** The Kaduna State Government, through the Kaduna State Schools Quality Assurance Authority (KSSQAA) and Ministry of Education, should immediately prioritise funding for reliable electricity (solar/inverter backup), high-speed internet connectivity, modern computers/tablets, and stable power supply in all public senior secondary school libraries.
2. **Compulsory Digital/Information Literacy Training:** There is a need for a structured, compulsory digital and information literacy programme covering citation management, database

searching, information evaluation, and digital navigation, which should be integrated into the SS1 and SS3 curriculum and delivered by trained teacher librarians with regular refresher workshops.

3. **Deployment of Inclusive and Modern Library Technologies:** KSSQAA should ensure immediate procurement and installation of assistive technologies (screen readers, braille embossers), remote access platforms, RFID systems, and smart library solutions, coupled with subscriptions to affordable or free academic databases and e-resources to eliminate digital exclusion.

References

- Abdulsalami, L. T., & Okezie, Q. I. (2023). Availability and utilisation of electronic information resources in secondary school libraries in North Central Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), 7890. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/7890>
- Abdullahi, Z., & Ogunniyi, S. (2023). Digital literacy competencies among senior secondary school students in Northern Nigeria: Implications for academic performance. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 9(3), 45–58.
- Adeniran, O. P. (2019). Academic library research support services: A review of Redeemer's University and the Nigeria Natural Medicine Development Agency's research activities. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), 2753. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/2753>
- Ali, N., & Naveed, M. A. (2020). Research support resources and services in university libraries of Pakistan: A situational analysis. *PLISJ*, 51 (ICEIL II Issue), 1–9.
- Babbie, E. (2020). *The practice of social research* (15th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Barbara, S. J., & Oberg, D. (2015). *IFLA school library guidelines* (2nd ed.). International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. [https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/school libraries resource centres/publications/ifla school library guidelines.pdf](https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/school%20libraries%20resource%20centres/publications/ifla%20school%20library%20guidelines.pdf)
- Chen, Y., & Deng, L. (2018). The use of ICT in libraries and its impact on information service delivery. *International Journal of Current Research and Technology*, 4(2), 45–52.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage.
- Eiriemiokhale, K. A., & Ibeun, M. O. (2022). Assessment of ICT facilities and e-library services in academic libraries in North West Nigeria. *International Journal of Knowledge Content Development & Technology*, 12(4), 45–60. <https://doi.org/10.5865/IJKCT.2022.12.4.045>
- Eze, J. U., & Uzoigwe, C. U. (2022). Information literacy skills of secondary school students in Kaduna State: A survey. *Nigerian School Library Journal*, 21(1), 112–128.
- Ezeala, L. O., & Yusuff, R. O. (2021). Challenges of integrating emerging technologies in school libraries: Implications for secondary education in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e journal), 5271. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/5271>
- Federal Ministry of Education and Youth Development. (2019). *Minimum standards for school libraries in Nigeria*. Federal Ministry of Education.
- Feldt, L. S., & Sedere, M. U. (2018). *Reliability in educational measurement*. Routledge.
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions. (2019). *IFLA school library guidelines* (2nd ed.). [https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/school libraries resource centres/publications/ifla school library guidelines.pdf](https://www.ifla.org/files/assets/school%20libraries%20resource%20centres/publications/ifla%20school%20library%20guidelines.pdf)

- Issa, A. O., Amusan, B., & Oluwatobi, S. O. (2021). Digital literacy and academic performance of secondary school students in Kwara State, Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(15), 78–89.
- Kaduna State Ministry of Education. (2023). *Kaduna State education sector analysis report 2022–2023*. Kaduna State Government.
- Koledoye, U. L., & Igwe, N. J. (2022). Perceived impact of contemporary library technology on academic performance of distance education undergraduates of universities in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal), 6773. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6773>
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 30(3), 607–610. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001316447003000308>
- Mahwasane, N. S., & Mudzielwana, N. R. (2016). Challenges of students in accessing information in the library: A brief review. *International Journal of Educational Sciences*, 15(3), 436–442. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09751122.2016.11890547>
- Merga, M. K. (2021). What is the literacy supportive role of the school librarian in the United Kingdom? *Journal of Librarianship and Information Science*, 53(3), 456–467. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0961000620964569>
- Nigerian Bureau of Statistics. (2025). *WAEC results statistics (2019–2021)*. <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng>
- Owate, C. N., & Okpa, I. (2013). The availability and utilisation of school library resources in some selected secondary schools in Rivers State. *Educational Research and Reviews*, 8(16), 1449–1460. <https://doi.org/10.5897/ERR2013.1522>
- Saunders, L. (2020). Core knowledge and specialised skills in academic libraries. *College & Research Libraries*, 81(2), 288–311. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.81.2.288>
- Shandu, L. Z. Z. (2014). Challenges in the provision of school library services in Katlehong secondary schools. *Mousaion*, 32(4), 13–28.
- Umar, A. M., & Audu, C. T. (2024). ICT infrastructure and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Kaduna metropolis: The role of school libraries. *Journal of Education in Developing Areas (JEDA)*, 32(1), 112–125.
- Uwakwe, E. O., Ume, T. E., & Nwosu, J. C. (2024). Information and communication technology and secondary school libraries in Nigeria: Issues and prospects. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 15(3), 85–95.
- Yakubu, M., & Dasuki, S. I. (2024). Assessing digital literacy levels among secondary school students in Northern Nigeria. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(4), 4567–4589. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12045-7>